

The Influence of Knowledge Management and Talent Management on Employee Performance in the Telecommunications Industry (Case Study: PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk)

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ABSTRACT: The rapid transformation of the telecommunications industry has increased the urgency for strategic human resource management to maintain organizational competitiveness and sustainability. This study explores the influence of knowledge management and talent management on employee performance within a leading telecommunications infrastructure company in Indonesia. A quantitative method was applied using Partial Least Squares – Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) to analyze responses from permanent employees collected through a structured questionnaire. The findings indicate that knowledge management plays a crucial and positive role in enhancing employee performance, particularly through knowledge creation, sharing, and application. In contrast, talent management was found to have a negative relationship with performance, suggesting possible misalignment in its implementation. Overall, the study emphasizes the importance of effective knowledge management in driving individual and organizational productivity, while also highlighting the need for a more responsive and strategic approach to talent management in adapting to the demands of the digital era.

KEYWORDS: Employee Performance, Human Resource Strategy, Knowledge Management, Talent Management, Telecommunications Industry

INTRODUCTION

The dynamic and highly competitive nature of the telecommunications industry necessitated the strategic management of human resources (HR) to maintain organizational competitiveness and adaptability amid continual change. A notable challenge observed was the decline in the proportion of employees categorized as “outstanding” and the corresponding increase in those classified as “meet target: at PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk during the 2019-2022 period, as evidenced by internal organizational data. This trend indicated a potential stagnation in employee performance, which may have impeded the attainment of strategic objectives if not addressed through a more robust and targeted HR management strategy.

The digital transformation in the era of Industry 4.0 was marked by a shift in the role of humans within organizations from merely functioning as executors to becoming key drivers of innovation and business sustainability. The emergence of a new industrial era, coupled with the rapid advancement of digitalization, was accompanied by significant changes in human roles, which were increasingly at risk of being replaced by digital technologies. The industry 4.0 era, which relied heavily on digital technologies, was even projected to eliminate more than 52 million types of jobs that had previously depended on human labor within the coming years [1]. This situation was implicitly interpreted to suggest that every individual was required to possess the willingness to develop skills and mental resilience that could not be replaced by technology as well as the ability to adapt to technological advancements, particularly in the digital domain. As a result, employees were enabled to retain their positions in the workforce and to collaborate productively with technology.

Challenges in human resource management were intensified by the advancement of digital technologies [2]. As stated in [3] assertion that companies were assigning increasingly demanding performance targets to employees to achieve their organizational vision and mission. Strategic capacity in the field of human resources was demonstrated through the preparation of individuals with strong competencies, adaptability, and high integrity are core values that were expected to be possessed by all employees.

In the era of accelerating global competition and disruption, companies were required not only to adapt but also to undergo strategic transformation. One of the critical aspects of this transformation was human resource management, which was positioned as key driver in achieving the company vision and mission. Superior human resources were expected not only to possess technical

competencies but also to demonstrate the ability to innovate, collaborate, and develop continuously. Therefore, it was considered essential for companies to establish human resource development strategies that were aligned with business needs and industry dynamics.

PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk, as one of the largest telecommunications infrastructure companies in Indonesia, had implemented various human resource development programs, including knowledge management and talent management. However, the effectiveness of these strategies in improving employee performance still needs to be further analyzed. Therefore, this study was conducted to empirically examine the influence of knowledge management and talent management on employee performance and to provide strategic recommendations for strengthening human resource capabilities in the digital era.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Human Resource Management

Human Resource Management (HRM) was defined as strategic process used to manage relationships and individual roles within organizations, including aspects of development, protection, and utilization of human resources to achieve corporate goals [4]. Gauzali as stated in to ensure that employees knowledge, skills, and competencies were aligned with company standards. It was also understood to include systematic processes of planning, recruitment, development, compensation, and termination of employment was considered an integral part of general management that focused on optimizing human capital as the organizations primary asset [6]. Furthermore, it was stated to encompass the selection, development, and maintenance of human resources to efficiently and ethically support the achievement of organizational objectives [7].

In general, the goal of HRM was not only to achieve organizational targets, but also to balance social and personal interests, such as protecting employee rights and creating a conducive work environment [5]. HRM was also viewed as playing a crucial role in ensuring all company policies were communicated and executed ethically and responsibly. Thus, HRM functioned as a strategic pillar that bridged organizational needs with individual potential and played a vital role in shaping workplace culture, enhancing productivity, and sustaining competitive advantage amid a dynamic business environment.

B. Knowledge Management

In general, knowledge management has been understood to encompass three interrelated and inseparable components: people, technology, and processes. Among these, the human element is considered the most critical, as the success of knowledge management largely depends on individual participation within the program [9]. It has been defined as a series of coordinated activities aimed at identifying, creating, and disseminating knowledge relevant to the organization, with the objective of enhancing employee capabilities in the workplace [6]. In addition, it was regarded as a systematic coordination process involving the management of human resources, processes, technology, and organizational structures, with the aim of increasing business value through training, knowledge sharing, and the application of existing expertise [7]. It was also interpreted as the process of organizing and distributing information and expertise tailored specifically to meet the company's needs. Thus, knowledge management was positioned as a series of processes aimed at creating, communicating, and applying knowledge that contributed to improved business value and employee performance [8].

Furthermore, knowledge management has been recognized as a strategic process that supports organizations in achieving their goals through the effective handling of knowledge [9]. It plays a vital role in enhancing employee performance, with studies indicating that performance can be optimized when employees possess the necessary knowledge. To ensure that knowledge management is implemented effectively, four essential knowledge processes must be addressed: knowledge acquisition, which includes gathering, discovering, and redesigning knowledge; knowledge conversion, referring to the ability to transform knowledge into more valuable and applicable forms; knowledge application, involving the efficient storage, utilization, and timely access to retained knowledge; and knowledge protection, which safeguards organizational knowledge from unauthorized access or misuse [10].

In addition, the concept of intellectual capital has been introduced as a complementary framework sharing a similar objective helping organizations to recognize and value their intangible assets through measurable indicators. Once quantified, these assets become easier to communicate and interpret. Several scholars have suggested that intellectual capital may serve as a representation of organizational performance and may function as an alternative approach to the balanced scorecard [11]. The dimensions of knowledge management were presented based on the framework developed in [12].

Table 1. The dimension of knowledge management [12]

No	Dimension	Description
1	Knowledge perception	The way knowledge was perceived, understood, and utilized by individuals
2	Knowledge gathering	The process by which information was gathered from various sources to support decision making.
3	Knowledge creation	Activities through which new knowledge was generated via research, discussion, and innovation.
4	Knowledge sharing	The distribution of information among individuals or teams was carried out to enhance collaboration and prevent duplication of work.
5	Knowledge diffusion	The dissemination of knowledge was expanded to enable its use across individuals or organizational units
6	Knowledge retention	Critical knowledge was preserved and stored to ensure its continued availability, particularly during personnel transitions within the organization.

C. Talent Management

Talent management was regarded as a strategic approach in human resource management, focusing on the identification, development, and retention of high-potential individuals. It was considered a method for providing accurate assessment of each employee working within the company [13]. When successfully implemented, talent management was found to yield strategic benefits for the organization, such as improving service quality delivered to customers, increasing customer satisfaction with the company’s products or services, enhancing productivity and business profitability, and creating a competitive advantage through employee development programs. Talent management was also viewed as part of strategic management, functioning to manage the talents possessed by the organization [14], with the objective of ensuring the availability of qualified human resources to fill both key and supporting positions within strategic functions. Based on these perspectives, it was concluded that talent management played a critical role in supporting organizational effectiveness through the structured, sustainable, and strategic management of high-performing employees. This positioned talent management as a key element in enhancing overall organizational performance. The three dimensions used to measure talent management were presented as follows [15]

Table 2. The dimension to measure talent management [15]

No	Dimension	Indicator	Description
1	Talent Acquisition	Talent needs planning	How individuals perceive, understand, and utilize knowledge.
		Employer branding	Building a positive image of the company as an attractive place to work.
		Recruitment strategy	The methods and channels used by the company to attract candidates, such as technology, social media, and partnerships with institutions.
		Talent selection	Assessing candidate fit not only based on technical qualifications but also values, potential, and organizational culture.
		Onboarding and initial orientation	Introducing new employees to the company’s culture, systems, and job roles.
2	Talent development	Development needs identification	The process of assessing the gap between employees’ current competencies and the competencies required.
		Training and learning provision	Formal training programs such as workshops, courses, certifications; the company actively provides learning opportunities.
		Coaching and mentoring	Individual development through guidance from supervisors or senior colleagues; employees receive support in decision-making and soft skills enhancement.
		Career development	Availability of clear and transparent career paths, including merit-based advancement, job rotation, and involvement in strategic projects.

3	Talent retention	Development effectiveness evaluation	Assessing the extent to which development programs have a measurable impact on individual performance and contribute to the company's goals.
		Job satisfaction	Employees' perceptions of their work, including workload, relationships with colleagues, and sense of pride in the company.
		Employee engagement	The extent to which employees feel emotionally connected to and committed to their work and the organization.
		Recognition and reward	Reflects how the company values individual contributions, including informal recognition such as bonuses, incentives, and promotions.
		Career development opportunities	Clear career paths positively impact the retention of talented employees in the workplace.
		Work life balance	Companies that support employee well-being through flexible working hours, fair leave policies, and psychological and health support tend to foster greater employee loyalty.

D. Employee Performance

Employee performance was associated with a strong sense of responsibility held by employees in achieving the company's vision and mission, along with obedience, punctuality in completing tasks, and the demonstration of honesty and high integrity in carrying out assigned duties. Employee performance was defined as the outcome produced by employees based on the quality and quantity of their work, as well as the responsibilities entrusted by the company [16]. It was also regarded as the result obtained by employees in accordance with the authority and responsibilities assigned to them, with the expectation that such performance would contribute to the company's goals without violating laws, norms, or existing regulations [3]. Based on these definitions, it was concluded that employee performance was a strategic concept used to build a positive working relationship between management and employees, with the aim of achieving strong performance outcomes. Good employee performance was seen as a reflection of the company's overall success in managing its business. The following section outlines the dimensions of employee performance [17].

Table 3. The dimension of employee performance [17]

No	Dimension	Description
1	Work quality	Assesses the extent to which employees outputs meet the standards set by the company.
2	Work quantity	Reflects the ability to complete tasks within the targeted timeframe, utilize work hours efficiently, and maintain consistent speed and endurance.
3	Responsibility	Demonstrates discipline, trustworthiness, and care for facilities and tools used. Employees are aware of the impact of their work and aligned with organizational goals.
4	Teamwork	Indicates openness to others opinions, willingness to assist colleagues, adaptability to group dynamics, and the ability to build positive working relationships.
5	Accountability	Measures employees awareness of assigned tasks and their commitment to completing them thoroughly and on time.

RESEARCH METHOD

The Partial Least Squares - Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) method was employed in this study to examine the influence of knowledge management and talent management on employee performance at PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk. Purposive sampling was used to select respondents, with the criterion that participants were permanent employees who had worked at the company for at least one year. A total of 85 respondents was considered sufficient for analysis using the PLS method.

Data were collected using a closed-ended questionnaire developed on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The instrument was constructed based on established theoretical frameworks. The knowledge management variable was measured through six dimensions adapted from Indiyati as cited in [12]: knowledge perception, knowledge gathering, knowledge creation, knowledge sharing, knowledge diffusion, and knowledge retention. The talent management variable referred

to three dimensions [15]: talent acquisition, talent development, and talent retention. Meanwhile, employee performance was measured using five dimensions [17]: work quality, work quantity, responsibility, teamwork, and discipline.

Instrument validity was assessed through expert judgment to ensure content relevance with the theoretical constructions, while reliability was evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values. Data analysis was conducted using SmartPLS 4.0, involving two primary stages: first, the evaluation of the measurement model (outer model) to test convergent validity, discriminant validity, and indicator reliability; and second, the evaluation of the structural model (inner model) to test the relationships among latent constructs using the coefficient of determination (R^2), effect size (f^2), and t-statistics obtained through bootstrapping. In accordance with the method referenced in [18].

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

A. Analysis of Structural Equation Modelling Partial Least Square

To evaluate the research hypotheses, a verification analysis was conducted based on statistical calculations. The hypotheses proposed in this study concerned the influence of knowledge management and talent management on employee performance at PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk. To analyze this relationship in greater depth, the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) statistical method and the Partial Least Squares (PLS) approach were applied. Based on the data processed using SmartPLS 3, the following results were obtained.

Figure 1. Structure of research variable

B. Outer Model Test

The measurement using the outer model was conducted to assess the reliability and validity of the research instrument. Four categories or criteria were considered in this evaluation: (1) convergent validity, (2) Cronbach's alpha, (3) composite reliability, and (4) discriminant validity.

Figure 2. Outer model from structural equation modeling (Algorithm)

1) Convergent Validity Test

This study demonstrated convergent validity as follows:

Table 4. The results of convergent validity test

Variable	Item Code	Outer Loading	Description
Knowledge Management	KM1	0,921	Valid
	KM2	0,935	Valid
	KM3	0,771	Valid
	KM4	0,858	Valid
	KM5	0,849	Valid
	KM6	0,880	Valid
	KM7	0,908	Valid
	KM8	0,939	Valid
	KM9	0,927	Valid
	KM10	0,826	Valid
	KM11	0,842	Valid
	KM12	0,911	Valid
	KM13	0,948	Valid
	KM14	0,935	Valid

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Item Code</i>	<i>Outer Loading</i>	<i>Description</i>
Talent Management	KM15	0,905	Valid
	TM1	0,932	Valid
	TM2	0,902	Valid
	TM3	0,891	Valid
	TM4	0,939	Valid
	TM5	0,956	Valid
	TM6	0,933	Valid
	TM7	0,912	Valid
	TM8	0,938	Valid
Employee Performance	TM9	0,753	Valid
	KK1	0,891	Valid
	KK2	0,950	Valid
	KK3	0,869	Valid
	KK4	0,942	Valid
	KK5	0,936	Valid
	KK6	0,890	Valid
	KK7	0,896	Valid
	KK8	0,953	Valid
	KK9	0,953	Valid
	KK10	0,930	Valid
	KK11	0,931	Valid
	KK12	0,939	Valid
KK13	0,913	Valid	

The values generated from the data analysis exceeded 0.5, were considered acceptable and regarded as valid items. Based on these results, the outer loading values in this study were deemed valid, as all indicators showed values above 0.5 [19].

2) *Discriminant Validity Test*

Based on the results obtained from Table 5, it was shown that all constructs in the study had values below 0.9. Therefore, the HTMT test values were considered to have met the required criteria, and the resulting discriminant validity was deemed acceptable.

Table 5. The result of discriminant validity test (HTMT)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)</i>
Knowledge management ↔ Employee performance	0,630
Talent management ↔ Employee performance	0,422
Talent management ↔ Knowledge management	0,834

3) *Reliability test*

Based on the reliability testing that was conducted, each variable showed Cronbach’s alpha and composite reliability values >0,7. These results indicated that the variables met the established criteria and were considered reliable.

Table 6. The result of reliability test

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Cronbach's alpha</i>	<i>Composite reliability</i>
Employee performance	0,961	0,965
Knowledge management	0,931	0,940
Talent management	0,953	0,961

The assessment of validity and reliability offered a solid groundwork for the analysis. The high Cronbach's Alpha scores reflected strong internal consistency among the measured items, confirming the constructs' reliability within the study. This methodological accuracy ensured the data was reliable and consistent, enabling trustworthy interpretation of the path coefficient analysis that followed [18].

C. Inner Model Test

Three evaluation measures were conducted to ensure that the data used adequately represented the variables examined in the study. The tests performed in the inner model included:

1) Bootstrapping Test (R^2)

Based on the data analysis conducted, an R^2 value of 0.395 was obtained. This result indicated that knowledge management and talent management had a moderate influence on employee performance, accounting for 39.5% of the variance. The remaining 60.5% was attributed to other variables that were not examined or included in the scope of this study.

Table 7. The result of bootstrapping test (R^2)

<i>Variable</i>	<i>R-square</i>	<i>R-square adjusted</i>
Employee performance	0,395	0,349

2) Q-squared Predictive Relevance

From the testing conducted, the obtained Q^2 value was greater than zero, indicating that the model used possessed predictive relevance.

Table 8. The result of Q^2 Predictive Relevance

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Q-Square</i>
Employee performance	0,315

3) Path Coefficient

In this study, the results of the test were presented in Table 9 as follows:

Table 9. The result of path coefficient

<i>Variable</i>	<i>P values</i>
Knowledge management → Employee performance	0,741
Talent management → Employee performance	-0,191

Based on the path coefficient analysis using SmartPLS, it was found that Knowledge Management (KM) had a strong and positive influence on employee performance, with a coefficient value of 0.741. This result indicated improvements in knowledge management practices. such as knowledge creation, storage, sharing, and application could significantly enhance individual performance within the organization. This finding aligned with the theory suggests that organizations capable of managing knowledge effectively were better positioned to adapt, solve problems, and drive overall employee productivity.

In contrast, Talent Management (TM) showed a negative coefficient value of -0.191 , indicating that improvements in talent management practices were negatively correlated with employee performance. This result did not support the initial hypothesis and suggested possible issues in the implementation of talent management within the organization. Overall, the findings highlighted the importance of systematic and strategic knowledge management as a key driver of improved employee performance, while also emphasizing the need for critical evaluation and improvement in talent management practices to ensure their positive contribution to performance outcomes.

These findings reflect the organization’s capacity to manage and leverage intangible assets, particularly through knowledge and talent. This aligns with the concept of intellectual capital, which has been developed to help organizations value and manage their intangible assets [11]. Intellectual capital can thus be interpreted as an alternative indicator of company performance, closely related to the balanced scorecard approach.

D. Hypothesis Testing

Table 10. Hypothesis testing result

<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>Path Coefficient</i>	<i>P value</i>	<i>Status</i>	<i>f-square</i>	<i>Impact</i>
Knowledge management → Employee performance	0,741	0,000	Accepted	0.309	Moderate
Talent management → Employee performance	-0,191	0,000	Accepted	0,020	Moderate

The hypothesis of this study is

1. The influence of Knowledge Management (X1) on Employee Performance (Y)

H₀: Knowledge management does not significantly affect employee performance.

H₁: Knowledge management affects employee performance.

2. The influence of Talent Management (X2) on Employee Performance (Y)

H₀: Talent management does not significantly affect employee performance.

H₁: Talent management affects employee performance.

The hypothesis testing results, obtained through the bootstrapping method, indicated that Knowledge Management had a significant effect on Employee Performance, with a path coefficient value of 0.741 and a p-value of 0.000 ($\alpha < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis (H_0) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (H_1) was accepted. An f-square value of 0.309 indicated that the effect size was categorized as moderate, leading to the conclusion that effective knowledge management contributed significantly to the improvement of employee performance.

Furthermore, the analysis revealed that Talent Management had a statistically significant but negative effect on Employee Performance, with a path coefficient of -0.191 and a p-value of 0.000. Although the relationship was negative, the hypothesis was statistically accepted, as the p-value was below 0.05. The f-square value of 0.020 indicated a weak effect, suggesting a possible misalignment in the implementation of talent management programs within the organization.

Simultaneously, an R^2 value of 0.395 showed that the combination of Knowledge Management and Talent Management explained 39.5% of the variance in Employee Performance. This result indicated that the structural model developed had acceptable validity and statistical significance, although other factors not included in the model were also likely to influence overall employee performance.

Table 11. Hypothesis testing on simultant variable results

<i>Hypothesis</i>	<i>R-square</i>	<i>R-square adjusted</i>	<i>Impact</i>
Knowledge Management dan talent management → Employee performance	0,395	0,349	Moderate

The hypothesis testing results showed that Knowledge Management and Talent Management jointly influenced Employee Performance, with an R-square value of 0.395 and an adjusted R-square value of 0.349. This R-square value indicated that 39.5% of the variability in Employee Performance could be explained by the two independent variables. Based on the interpretation criteria for R-square, the magnitude of this influence was categorized as moderate.

Figure 3. Bootstrapping result

PLS-SEM analysis showed that knowledge management had a significant and positive impact on employee performance at PT Dayamitra Telekomunikasi Tbk, with a path coefficient of 0.741 and a p-value of 0.000. The effect size was moderate ($f^2 = 0.309$), indicating that effective knowledge sharing, documentation, and utilization improved employee outcomes. Measurement indicators were valid and reliable, supported by high outer loadings (> 0.7), composite reliability (0.940), and Cronbach’s alpha (0.931). These findings highlight that knowledge management played a key role in enhancing productivity, as supported by previous findings [20]. Meanwhile, talent management showed a statistically significant but negative effect on employee performance (path coefficient = -0.191 ; p-value = 0.000; $f^2 = 0.020$). Although measurement indicators were valid, the weak and negative influence suggests misalignment between talent programs and employee expectations. Factors such as lack of career development opportunities or inequitable systems may explain the negative perception. Effective career planning and supportive environments are crucial for boosting performance [21]. Together, knowledge and talent management explained 39.5% of the variance in employee performance ($R^2 = 0.395$), indicating moderate predictive strength. While knowledge management contributed positively and substantially, talent management’s impact was minimal and negative. These results underscore the importance of integrating both strategies effectively to create a supportive and high-performing work environment.

Simultaneously, knowledge and talent management explained 39.5% of the variance in employee performance ($R^2 = 0.395$), indicating moderate predictive strength. While knowledge management contributed positively and substantially, talent management’s impact was minimal and negative. These results underscore the importance of integrating both strategies effectively to create a supportive and high-performing work environment. This finding is in line with previous research, which argues that if knowledge management is not implemented optimally, it can disrupt workflow, reduce employee morale, and ultimately lower performance at both the individual and team levels [22].

CONCLUSION

This study confirms that knowledge management significantly and positively affects employee performance ($p = 0.000$; $f^2 = 0.309$), while talent management has a significant but negative and weak effect ($p = 0.000$; $f^2 = 0.020$). Combined, both variables explain 39.5% of the variance in performance ($R^2 = 0.395$), indicating moderate predictive power. The measurement model showed good validity and reliability, with acceptable indicator loadings, composite reliability, and HTMT values. The predictive relevance ($Q^2 = 0.315$) further supports the model's usefulness for HR decision-making. These findings highlight the need to strengthen knowledge systems and realign talent strategies to improve employee outcomes.

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